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HIV/AIDS, Security, and the United States of America

Abstract

This paper debates on how pandemics like HIV/AIDS have become an important security concern for many countries and especially the United States of America. While the focus here, is on this particular epidemic, which has shaken international politics since the 1980s, it takes a more generic approach to what measures states undertake when it comes to protecting their interests, their jurisdictional geo-spatial spaces and the people governed by them. The humanitarian side of it is of course acknowledged, but along with that comes state interests, which transcend humanitarian beliefs and ethics. The relationship between humanitarian ethics and security has been kept so ambiguous and blurred in formal writings on the subject, that the various dimensions of security are often ignored by states. Often, under the pretext of economic growth and military expansion, individual wellbeing of the people being governed is equated merely with the state's interest in productivity. The stronger states, in their efforts to alleviate the weaker ones, customarily patronize the latter, thereby creating a wider gap and disparity, leading to further dependence.

Keywords: *HIV/AIDS, Epidemic, Humanitarian, Security, USA.*

Introduction

The idea of sovereignty is perhaps as old as the idea of the formation of the states itself. Respect for sovereignty and non-interference in each other's administrative jurisdiction are the cardinal principles on which the states exist as independent entities and what they fundamentally demand of each other. Like mediaeval times, modern democratic nations pursue the same old strategy for survival and self-protection, but often, this is done in the guise of humanitarian

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and welfare measures, which are used as an excuse to impose, control, suppress, and finally to invade. When it comes to health, the need for security and humanity go hand in hand. No doubt, strategic protection from infectious diseases has necessitated global intervention but the definition of security is so ambiguous, that global actors have manipulated it to influence not only individual consciousness but the global consciousness as well. In this context, the relationship between HIV/AIDS and national security gains importance, the reason being its slow incubation period, history of incurability, its devastating impact on individuals, groups, communities, institutions and nations at large, and finally because of the fear of its global transmission. In the present-day scenario, international relations are no longer defined as the cat and mouse game of the past and with the development of human and state ethics, perhaps the idea of security has also changed; from the very obscurantist to a relatively progressive one. (In terms of comparison and not in the absolute sense of the words) This however did not happen in a vacuum, but through decades of intellectual and political discourses on the Public Health System.

In the field of international relations, security is understood through the perspective of the state, while HIV/AIDS is looked at more through a political lens, where the intervention in its prevention and treatment is not entirely on humanitarian grounds, but largely supplemented by the idea that a pandemic can influence internal security too (McInnes, 2006), destroy labour productivity and hinder national growth.¹ This has led to the unfortunate practice of quarantining weaker states by the more developed ones.

The Approaches to Security and HIV/AIDS

Constructivists take an objective view of military interventions and the power struggle exhibited by powerful states, but also focus on the subjective meaning of security as fabricated by states, societies, or individuals, based on their historical, cultural, or psychological understanding of intimidation and security. (Lo and Yuk, 2015) Recognising the importance of health to national security, states now include health as an integral component of military strategy. In the post-Cold War period, modern nation states have become increasingly concerned about the security issues relating to global public health, especially when it comes to addressing the spread and containment of infectious diseases. Hence, every approach to deal with an infectious disease being followed be it leprosy or HIV/AIDS, it would appear to become a security concern.

What also compels critical attention is the way economic interests, like health interests, have merged with the larger security aspects. McInnes and Rushton (2011) argue that the concept of security has changed from a classical

military definition to a broader approach which includes the not so well-defined factors influencing the socio-political environment such as the physical environment, food, and migration, to name a few. To that extent modern approaches by states are confronted by the disquieting question: 'What is not a security issue?' Experts on the subject have said that even though health, as a human security issue, has a humanitarian flavour, it must connect to national security. McInnes (2006) claims that pandemics like HIV/AIDS are more easily transmitted in conflict prone areas and hence sensitive to military and national security. It would appear that we are living in an age of deception and contradictions where security is the mask under which health strategies too, find a convenient refuge.

In her article entitled, 'What contribution can International Relations make to the evolving global health agenda?' Davies and Fidler mention two approaches towards public health in the international arena—the 'statist' approach and the global approach. The former mainly focuses on the security aspect where the health aspect is considered a mere strategy in a nation's overall foreign and defence policy. They portray weak states as being largely dependent on stable governance for their good health and conclude that they are, by implication, poor protectors of health. That is why the statist approach empowers states to put forward their public health agenda by securitization of the area commonly called 'high politics.' (Davies, 2001; Fidler, 2004) Though the globalist approach acknowledges various aspects of health concerns in the everyday lives of the people and is sensitive towards the individual's health needs and expects the state to cater to those needs in a humanitarian manner, it does not necessarily consider the state as being vital to the needs of individuals. While the global approach does not entirely reject the importance of national security, it does not concur with the exclusivity of the 'statist' approach of *securitization* of states. In the case of infectious diseases, the globalists analyse it in their own right and argue that regardless of the fact of who is infected, it is important that intervention be carried out in the name of humanity. The statist, on the other hand, as Davies points out, is focussed on protecting a specific group or population to whom it is accountable.

Developed nations strongly believe that HIV/AIDS is posing a major threat to the global social environment and its psycho-social well being, which is detrimental to the stability of states or regions.² They have coined the term 'hollowing out' to describe the socio-economic impact of effective production, caused by illnesses and premature death (Vieira 2007) on the state institutions by the loss of life. This, they claim is leading to deviant behaviour in the youth³ and the increasing problem of orphaned children of parents dying from HIV/

AIDS⁴; all further having a detrimental impact on the military services of the states. (Rushton 2001) DuPont (2001) points out that if the prevalence of HIV/AIDS continues to expand further in East Asia, it will increase the poverty levels, intensify the problem of resource allocation, and thereby have an overall impact on the democratisation process of the regions. This will not only add to the national security concerns of individual states but it will also affect the collective national security. While these countries are suppressed under the ruthless arms of poverty, poor public health attracts big corporates and governments from developed nations, (DuPont, IBID) who, as a political strategy, offer economic benefits in the guise of their securitization and humanitarian policies. (DuPont, 2001; Fidler, 2004; Rushton, 2000).

The Changing Nature of State Approach to Security and HIV/AIDS: A Tale of American Interest

The HIV/AIDS pandemic has not only affected individuals, but, over the years, has impacted the psycho-social, economic and national development of many potential societies, leaving large parts of the world in a post-traumatic condition. Unlike other pandemics, when we talk about security in the context of HIV/AIDS, we must take into account various aspects of individual, family, community, economic, military, and global health security, which influence individual behaviour, institutional and structural orientation and overall societal wellbeing. Security being associated with HIV/AIDS has seen the emergence of new policies influenced by health and medical experts, leading to a wider process of *medicalization*. (Elbe, 2011).

Among the security concerns associated with HIV/AIDS, the technical aspect of security in its different perspectives has been discussed in many scholarly dissertations. Often the term security is associated with national and global security (Cecchine and Moore, 2006) almost completely, or at least partially, ignoring the most fundamental aspect of security, which should be family and societal security. This is so, mainly owing to the fact that the major focus has been appropriated by military and institutional concerns, which are considered as the essential foundation of national security by world leaders. The pandemic is no longer merely a humanitarian crisis, but a security crisis that emerges from the larger consciousness of the state to protect itself and its institutional interests.⁵

In the process, personal security, which is related to human life span and productivity and forms the basis of individual wellbeing, gets increasingly threatened by a pandemic like HIV/AIDS. The 108th Congress of the United States of America, in its capitalist mode of comprehension of public health, and particularly infectious diseases, pointed out that HIV/AIDS can be a major threat

to national productivity, which could lead to losses in the growing business of the country. The Congress, although it acknowledged the importance of individual wellbeing, considered it from the perspective of labour and productivity, and did not hesitate in pointing out that the pandemic is a threat to international business and security, not forgetting to mention its effect on the American military under the UN peace keeping forces deployed in war-torn underdeveloped countries of Africa and Asia. Section 2, Article 10 of the Congress mentions how the American military under the UN peace keeping force has a greater likelihood of getting infected in those environments in which it operates.

The idea here is to analyse how the United States' concept of security is confined to the economic boundaries defined by capitalist interests and American internationalism. Authors like Fieldbaum (2006) and others have pointed out the hypocritical nature of the United States and its duality in failing to identify non-communicable diseases that are a threat to national security. As mentioned earlier, developed nations like the United States have used military intervention for their own economic expansion, but in the guise of humanitarian concern. To address the prevention and treatment of HIV/AIDS the emphasis has shifted from the Western Phalian approach which was based on the principle of non-interference in the sovereignty of nations and respect for self-determination to the Post-Western Phalian approach wherein aspects of human rights have been given prime importance. (Fidler, 2004) The United States of America came a long way from being a nation which had neglected the HIV/AIDS pandemic during the Reagan administration to a more progressive humanitarian Obama administration. But again, it has become very apathetic and regressive under the Trump administration. Over the years, the idea of America's National security as a state strategy has been the focus of attention and has taken precedence over the humanitarian and ethical path. In this however, the American ideals, interests and internationalism had always been of prime concern, especially the protection of American military from infection during its operations in Africa and Asia.

Though the US was involved in securing itself from the HIV/AIDS pandemic it was only during the 1990s (Rushton, 2000; Fidler, 2004; Vieira, 2007) that the HIV/AIDS-security linkage became apparent in Washington policy circles. Some of those involved in pushing forward the case complained that the Clinton administration was somewhat slow on the uptake. Though the argument was gaining ground, such a pandemic concerning global public health did not receive the kind of attention it demanded from a global power like the United States of America. In fact, the regressive mind-set of the American administration was only too evident. In 1982, in an interview with the journalist and radio host

Lester Kinsolving, Larry Speakes, Press Secretary to Ronald Reagan, could not resist making fun of the HIV/AIDS pandemic as a ‘gay disease’ and mocking those suffering from it. (Lopez, 2016) Even after that, there was very little effort made by the Reagan administration to address the HIV/AIDS problem and it was only years later, in 1990, that the Ryan White Care Act⁶ was launched in America during President George H. W. Bush’s tenure.

Recognising the serious threat posed by HIV/AIDS, the Clinton administration (1993-2001) increased the funds for the prevention and treatment of HIV/AIDS and also put in place other measures to combat the pandemic. America’s idea of security as a component of HIV/AIDS prevention and treatment has its genesis in the United States Ambassador to the United Nations, Richard Holbrooke’s visit to Africa in 1999 to get an overview of the AIDS outbreak in that country.⁷ It was Holbrooke who redefined the HIV/AIDS pandemic as world-wide as well as an internal stability threat, though most give President Clinton credit for it. It was his seminal observation of the condition of the US military in the UN peace keeping forces in Cambodia⁸ and Africa and his continuous persuasion of the Secretary-General of the United Nations, Kofi Annan, that led to the UN Security Council Resolution 1308⁹ being passed in July 2000 and the pandemic being included as a threat to international peace and security. (Vieira, 2007; Cecchine and Moore, 2006).

During this period, the situation in Africa had grown so serious that there were more deaths from HIV/AIDS than from civil conflicts. In December 2004, the UN Secretary-General’s High-Level Panel Report on Threats, Challenges and Change, highlighted the need for immediate intervention to deal with the pandemic and to protect state and societies through proper research and planning and action taken to reduce the impact of the endemic in the long run. (Tony Barnett and Gwyn Prins, 2006) This was an event of paramount importance because, for the first time, the popular notion of public health and development was brought under the ambit of international security. (Stefan Elbe, 2006).

US Perspectives on HIV/AIDS and Security

Although the Security Council had started monitoring the securitization process, its efforts were half-hearted and non-committal. Rushton (2000) argues that discourses around the securitization of HIV/AIDS have been far less successful than it is often supposed. Meanwhile, though the security threats posed by the African nations on the United States vis-a-vis, HIV/AIDS had been widely debated, from the period of the Clinton administration, there was a gradual shift in US thinking, with attention being diverted from Africa to countries like India, Russia and China where the US saw greater opportunities

for involvement to further their economic interests. It is no secret that the US designs its strategies and re-defines its core and peripherals based on its own interests, and though sub-Saharan Africa was most important to the national security debate it was ultimately peripheral. (Fidler, 2003).

The United States has repeatedly, time and again pointed out that infectious diseases endanger its citizens at home and abroad and also puts the US armed forces deployed in different missions, overseas, at risk. Infectious diseases exacerbate social and political instability in regions where the US has been showing interest. While infectious diseases are addressed in terms of interventions, one cannot say the same for non-communicable diseases as far as US interventions are concerned. Such strategic focus by the US has isolated important global health problems that exhibit high morbidity and mortality. The lack of interest shown to non-communicable diseases by powerful states like the US in developing countries only goes to prove that non-communicable diseases do not meet their strategic interests and hence the politics hidden in the guise of security and humanitarianism becomes quite evident.

During the initial years of the detection of HIV/AIDS, it was relegated to the category of public health and development in the US and was not given due importance. Though the US Central Intelligence Agency endeavoured to link HIV/AIDS with security in the 1990s, it could not get the attention it required until 2000 in the form of the 1308 resolution. (Fidler, 2004; Cecchine, Moore, 2006) A National Intelligence Council report entitled, 'The Global Infectious Disease Threat and its Implications for the United States', which supported the Clinton Administration's portrayal of HIV/AIDS as a global security threat, analysed the devastating internal impact caused by the HIV/AIDS pandemic. (Vieira, 2007) Developing nations, immigrants and retired US personnel were held responsible for its spread and the report claimed that it not only had a tremendous impact on internal security and the military, but also on the very socio-political fabric of the United States of America. (John C. Gannon, 2000).

However, scholars like Susan Peterson argued that such a portrayal of the pandemic was exaggerated and maybe slightly overestimated, and that the security implications had insufficient arguments to support it, which might only fuel suspicion, rivalry and conflict between states, thereby triggering other security concerns. She advocated a more progressive approach in dealing with the issue, through better multi-national co-operation. Peterson further argued that responding to pandemics like HIV/AIDS only through the perspective of national security would, in the long run, discourage nations and eliminate the chance of states addressing public health issues in their own right. The garrisoning of states over human rights might provide them the opportunity to be vigilant,

but they could abdicate from the moral responsibility that they should have towards the weak and the vulnerable. Peterson, in this regard, argues that the nation-states should strengthen their capacity to actually face the pandemic rather than securitizing states against it. States should come up with interventional plans to deal with the pandemic for what it is and recognize the unprecedented tragedy it could bring and endeavour to build a network of international humanitarian assistance to solve the problem of HIV/AIDS. (Susan Peterson, 2002).

Concluding Remarks and Concerns

The idea of security has always been a major concern for countries like the United States. On one hand, the United States has extended support to developing countries through its different policies, but on the other, it has also engaged in manipulating, re-constructing and re-orienting the idea of security by putting too much focus on the technical aspects pertaining to national security, and through it all, has missed the essentials of human rights and humanitarianism. The United States has not been able to address the global HIV/AIDS pandemic in recent years in the way it has been expected to, and American Internationalism, hidden in the sympathetic nature portrayed by Bush or the empathetic nature of Obama is no less harmful than the outwardly ignorant attitude of President Reagan in the early 1980s and the very apathetic nature of President Trump today. The intention here is not to discredit or belittle the efforts of successive American governments, but to better appreciate the fact that the concept of security should not remain confined to the American notion of security, which focuses on mere labour productivity, capital expansion and military security.

Along with the complexities of imposing the responsibility on developing nations, the United States has also been discriminatory in its approach within its own boundary. Although this is not an important aspect in this paper, it is nonetheless a matter of concern, which reflects the plight faced by people of developing countries when it comes to addressing the problem of the HIV/AIDS pandemic. The ethical question related to the securitization of HIV/AIDS is well mentioned by Elbe (2011) who traces the cases of discrimination and marginalization faced by countries of suspect, as in the case with Haitians in the United States, who are denied housing or other basic facilities of life and sometimes even dismissed from jobs.

Similar was the fate of Africans in Europe who were denied basic rights because of the fear of them being HIV/AIDS carriers.¹⁰ The practice of discrimination followed by countries like the United States, who, on the one hand, portray themselves as torch bearers of the humanitarian philosophy, and on the other, discriminate against migrants and settlers infected by HIV is

definitely a form of double standard, a paradox and oxymoronic in the American context. It is contradictory because it is a well-established fact that HIV/AIDS has definite criteria for infection and people cannot be infected through the physical environment and, therefore, discriminating against certain ethnic groups, for example and not providing them houses, and other basic amenities is an act which reflects racist perceptions associated with HIV/AIDS.

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Notes

1. United Nations special session on HIV/AIDS, June 2001.
http://www.un.org/ga/aids/ungassfactsheets/html/fssecurity_en.htm, and the One Hundred Tenth Congress of the United States of America held in the City of Washington on Thursday, 03 January 2008,
<https://www.pepfar.gov/documents/organization/108294.pdf>.
2. 108 Congress of the United States of America held in Washington DC, 2003, <https://www.congress.gov/bill/108th-congress/house-bill/1298>.
3. Adewole, “Public health, national security interlinked”, *New Telegraph*, September 2018, <https://newtelegraphonline.com/2018/09/public-health-national-security-interlinked-adewole/>.
4. AIDS as a security threat, United Nations Special Session on HIV/AIDS, Global Crisis-Global Action, June 2001, New York, http://www.un.org/ga/aids/ungassfactsheets/html/fssecurity_en.htm.
5. Speech by US Vice President Al Gore during the UN Security Council meeting, 10 January 2000.
6. About the Ryan White HIV/AIDS Program, date last reviewed October 2016, <https://hab.hrsa.gov/about-ryan-white-hiv-aids-program/about-ryan-white-hiv-aids-program>.
7. Interview: Richard Holbrooke, *The Frontline*, 30 May 2006,
<https://www.pbs.org/wgbh/pages/frontline/aids/interviews/holbrooke.html>.
8. Ibid.
9. UN Security Council Resolution 1308 (2000) on the Responsibility of the Security Council in the Maintenance of International Peace and Security: HIV/AIDS and International Peace-keeping Operations Security Council Distr.: General 17 July 2000,
http://www.unaids.org/sites/default/files/sub_landing/files/20000717_un_sresolution_1308_en.pdf.
10. Ibid.

References

1. T Barnett and G. Prins, “HIV / AIDS and Security: Fact, Fiction and Evidence: A Report to UNAIDS”, *International Affairs* (Royal Institute of International Affairs 1944-), Vol. 82, No. 2, HIV/AIDS-Special Issue, 2006, pp. 359-368, Oxford University Press on behalf of the Royal Institute of International Affairs, Accessible at: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3569426>, accessed on 22 November 2017.

2. G. W. Brown and R. Labonté, “Globalization and its methodological discontents: Contextualizing globalization through the study of HIV/AIDS”, *Globalization and Health*, 7, 29, 2011, <http://doi.org/10.1186/1744-8603-7-29>.
3. N.G. Cecchine and M. Moore, “Technical Report on Infectious Disease and National Security Strategic Information”, prepared for the Office of the Secretary of Defence Approved for public release, National Defence Research Institute, Rand Corporation, 2006. https://www.rand.org/content/dam/rand/pubs/technical_reports/2006/RAND_TR405.pdf.
4. S.E. Davies, “What contribution can International Relations make to the evolving global health agenda, International Affairs”, *Royal Institute of International Affairs*, Vol. 86, No. 5, 2010, pp. 1167-1190, Oxford University Press on behalf of the Royal Institute of International Affairs, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/40865133>.
5. A. DuPont, *East Asia Imperilled: Transnational Challenges to Security*, Cambridge, Cambridge University Press, 2001.
6. Stefan Elbe, “Should HIV/AIDS Be Securitized? The Ethical Dilemmas of Linking HIV/AIDS and Security”, *International Studies Quarterly*, Vol. 50, No. 1, 2006, pp. 119-144, Wiley on behalf of The International Studies Association, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3693554>.
7. Stefan Elbe, “Pandemics on the Radar Screen: Health Security, Infectious Disease and the Medicalisation of Insecurity”, *Political Studies*, 59, 4, 2011, pp. 848-866.
8. H. Feldbaum, K. Lee and P. Patel, “The National Security Implications of HIV/AIDS”, *PLoS Med* 3(6): e171, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pmed.0030171>.
9. D. P. Fidler, “Racism or Realpolitik – U.S. Foreign Policy and the HIV/AIDS Catastrophe in Sub-Saharan Africa”, *Gender Race & Justice*, 97, 2003, p. 148.
10. D.P. Fidler, “Fighting the Axis of Illness: HIV/AIDS, Human Rights, and U.S. Foreign Policy”, Maurer Faculty, Paper 400, 2004, <http://www.repository.law.indiana.edu/facpub/400>.
11. John C. Gannon, “The Global Infectious Disease Threat and Its Implications for the United States”, NIE 99-17D, January 2000, <https://fas.org/irp/threat/nie99-17d.htm>.
12. G. Lopez, “The Reagan administration’s unbelievable response to the HIV/AIDS epidemic”, *Vox*, 2016, <https://www.vox.com/2015/12/1/9828348/ronald-reagan-hiv-aids>.
13. C. McInnes and S. Rushton, “HIV/AIDS and securitization theory”, *European Journal of International Relations*, 19(1), 2011, pp. 115–138, <http://journals.sagepub.com/doi/pdf/10.1177/1354066111425258>.
14. C. McInnes, “HIV/AIDS and security”, *European Journal of International Relations*, 2006, <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1468-2346.2006.00533.x>.
15. Susan Peterson, “Epidemic Disease and National Security”, *Journal of Security Studies*, vol. 12, no. 2, 2002, pp. 43-81.
16. S. Rushton, “AIDS and international security in the United Nations System”, *Health Policy and Planning*, Vol. 25, Issue 6, 1 November 2010, pp. 495–504, <https://doi.org/10.1093/heapol/czq051>.
17. Tony Barnett and Gwyn Prins, “HIV / AIDS and Security: Fact, Fiction and Evidence: A Report to UNAIDS”, *International Affairs* (Royal Institute of International Affairs 1944), Vol. 82, No. 2, HIV/AIDS-Special Issue (March 2006), pp. 359-368, published by: Oxford University Press on behalf of the Royal Institute of International Affairs, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3569426>.

18. A.M. Vieira, "The Securitization of the HIV/AIDS Epidemic as a Norm: A Contribution to Constructivist Scholarship on the Emergence and Diffusion of International Norms", *Brazilian Political Science Review*, vol. 2, Rio De Jenerio, 2007, http://socialsciences.scielo.org/pdf/s_bpsr/v2nse/a05v2nse.pdf.
19. C Yuk and P. Lo, *HIV/AIDS in China and India Governing Health Security*, Palgrave Macmillan Publication, New York, 2015.